
ALGORITHMIC GOVERNMENT APPROACH: AUTOMATING PUBLIC SERVICES AND SUPPORTING CIVIL SERVANTS WITH AI TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract: The current era is the era of digital innovation, especially Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a new technology is widely using by governments to improve government operations, create secure, convenient, and quality public services. This study explores how AI can be used in government service, particularly in automating public services and supporting civil servants through AI-based technologies. Also, the paper conducts survey and analyzes literatures, and international experiences in providing high-quality services to citizens. This paper aims to analyze and identify the role of AI technologies in government services. At the same time, we propose Algorithmic Governance Approach based on AI technologies (AGA-AI) and make proposal. This is a new approach to improve the quality of public services and assist civil servants’ performance. The contribution of this paper is to give a proposal on improve service quality, and simple procedures in governance.

Keywords: algorithmic governance, digital innovation, digital transformation, artificial intelligence, leadership.

Introduction

Innovativeness is the most important factor in the development of every country in the world. New technologies bring new opportunities for government and citizens. At the present time, Governments around the world are exploring new ways and approaches to utilize algorithms to enhance public services, streamline operations efficiently, improve resource allocation, enhance policy outcomes, create and fast analyze complex data sets, make more effective decisions, and reduce bias in their government systems. The term "algorithm" in English, in Latin translation "algoritmic", in origin "algebra" is derived from the name of the mathematician Muhammad ibn Musa al-Khwarizmi “father of algebra”, who lived in the 9th century in Khorazm (the region of Uzbekistan) [1]. Currently, algorithms have become even more significant in our digitized world.

Algorithmic governance is a form of government to use computer algorithms (AI, big data, data knowledge) for regulations, law enforcement, and others [2], [3]. The significant of algorithmic governance is to improve efficiency, and transparency,

fairness in the decision-making processes by analyzing large datasets and the identifying patterns [4]. The main idea of this study is to comparative analyze and find new ways on using AI technologies in government services. We propose new approach on algorithmic government based on our previous researches and experiences. The contributions of this paper are as follows: we propose AI technology-based Algorithmic Government Approach (AGA-AI) for the use of algorithms to manage, secure and more efficient government services; AI has a relevant role in achieving the most prominent vision of government services, which is to improve service quality and simple procedures.

related works

This section reviews related resources, analysis conducted surveys and comparison, and finding new ways of algorithmic government in public administration. In today’s fast-paced digital era, emerging technologies play a crucial role in building a positive bridge between government and citizens for effective, inclusive, and accountable support peoples with services. Every public organization [5] needs innovation for effective operation and to launch new projects, services, and products. AI is the broader concept of machines can be able to perform tasks like human intelligence that computer systems to automatically can learn and make predictions or decisions based on huge amount of data. According to scholars Montaya et al.,[6], Tanja et. al.,[7], Ojo et al.,[8], Yanqin Duan et al.,[9] governments across the world are paying more attention AI-based technologies to improve the quality of public services, to foster citizens’ trust and to increase efficiency and effectiveness in service delivery.

Algorithmic government was first learned by Zeynep Engin et al., [10], who proposed an alternative form of government or social ordering where the usage of computer algorithms is applied to regulations, law enforcement, and generally any aspect of everyday life. This approach has studied in data science sphere. It provides practical guidance on how governments can implement AI technologies in responsible ways [11]. Ahn and Chen [12] identify nine different uses of AI in government settings. These include smart allocation of public service resources, digital assistance with chatbots, pattern identification and predictive analytics models, automation and smart public services, smart energy, and internet of things, robotics sensors, autonomous driving, and sensor-based detection and prevention. Similarly, Bernd Wirtz et al., [13] also emphasis specific AI applications and how they implement in the public sector. AI in public services has the potential to support civil servants and increase service quality for citizens. Gomes de Sousa [14] argue that policy, ethical principles of AI-based applications are important including AI techniques, AI solutions to support public services, and the actual functions of government.

This study conducts survey and a peer review of scientific papers (such as research databases) on AI-based technologies for automating public service and supporting civil servants. This study doesn’t only learn to enhance the efficiency of the government services but also improve civil servants to better serve the needs of citizens.

proposed method

In this section, we analyze literatures, advanced international experiences and conduct survey on the potential impacts of AI technologies for automating public services and supporting civil servants in government services during the today’s fast digital era.

Figure 1. AGA-AI Approach

Figure 2 AI Tree

the vision of algorithmic governance approach

Algorithmic Approach (Inn=Inness+DIIn+AI+ML+DL+BiD+DSc+CyS)

Innovation (Inn) the word “innovation” is derived from the Latin verb “innovate”, which means to “renew”. Innovation is a process, product, or service that is renewed; it also introduces new techniques, and creative new ideas. It is important for improving the efficiency, providing new and quality services, etc. [15].

Digital Innovation (DIIn) is the use of digital technologies, and new applications to improve existing processes and efficiency, enhance citizen satisfaction, and launch new products or businesses. New emerging technology can be considered a digital innovation from wearable devices to conversational chatbots, apps. [16].

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a machine that is capable of thinking like humans. AI is a subset of data science; it was defined by Marvin Minsky and John McCarthy in the 1950s. AI is characterized as the main driver of emerging technologies and can perform tasks that typically require human intelligence. AI has the potential to modernize numerous sectors, such as healthcare (diagnosis), finance (fraud detection), transportation (autonomous vehicles), customer service (chatbots, virtual and robo-assistants), and etc. [17]. The levels of AI are *Narrow or Weak AI* (currently, AI focuses on performing specific/narrow tasks such as image recognition,

route planning, internet searches, and autonomous vehicles). *General or Strong AI* (the near future, it can perform almost all the intellectual tasks like humans such as recognition, analyzing, decision-making, the ability to solve problems, learning, and planning for the future). *Super or Very Strong AI* (future of AI), it will have capability more than humans. This system will be the highpoint of AI and it will be able to do everything because of tremendously great memory, fast data processing, analysis, and decision-making capabilities.

Machine Learning (ML) is a subset of AI that focuses on learning from and making predictions or decisions based on data without being explicitly programmed. It enables systems to analyze large amounts of data quickly and accurately, improve decision-making processes, and automate complex tasks. Arthur Samuel [18] was recognized first by the term “Machine Learning”. *Deep Learning (DL)* is a subfield of machine learning that focuses on training artificial neural networks to learn automatically and make predictions or decisions from analyzing large amounts of data. It allows the machine to engage huge amounts of unstructured data such as text, images, audio, and more [19].

Big Data (BiD) refers to extremely large and complex data sets. The concept of big data expanded in the early 2000s when industry analyst Doug Laney announced the definition of big data as the three Vs: **volume, velocity, and variety**. Data originates in all types of formats from structured, numeric data in traditional databases to unstructured text documents, emails, videos, audios, stock ticker data, financial transactions [20]. *Data Science (DSc)* is a multidisciplinary field of computer science that uses scientific methods, processes, algorithms, and systems to extract knowledge and insights from structured and unstructured data. The keys of data science are data collection, cleaning, analysis, modeling, interpreting, visualization and machine learning [21].

Cyber-Security (CyS) is the protection systems, application of technologies, processes to control and protect systems, networks, programs, devices, and data. It aims to reduce the risk of cyber-attacks and protect against the unauthorized exploitation of systems, networks, and technologies [22].

Administrative Approach

(Ldp=SmM+HCM+PM+StM+TM+RsM+PjM+MotInc)

Leadership and Smart Management (Ldp & SmM) are core skills to influence a group for the achievement of goals. Leader drives new approaches, ideas, and creativity to practice. Management implements it to achieve better results in the organization. An effective leader creates a clear direction for their organization [23]. The following types of management were selected as a core based on our previous researches:

Human Capital Management (HCM) is to designate personal attributes considered useful in the production process, and it increases productivity and profitability through education, training, intelligence, experiences, health, personal skills (communication, flexibility, adaptability, problem-solving, critical thinking, professionalism, teamwork, work ethics), and others [24]. *Performance Management (PM)* is a common function of human resources and it increases responsibilities and results. PM develops objective setting, communication, and tutoring for better performance, and operation of employee development programs, and rewarding achievements. PM is defined as a management system of processes that is aimed at enhancing performance in an organization [25].

Strategic Management (StM) is a vision for all divisions of the organization, covering every administrative system and process of managing an organization's innovation procedure. It motives to investigate the public sector's ability to innovate and achieve innovativeness and goals [26]. *Time Management (TM)* is a process of planning, arranging, and conscious control of time spent on precise activities, particularly to increase efficiency, effectiveness, and productivity. Administrative time management is the skill of identifying, valuing, and reducing time-cost waste inside organizations. The POSEC method was introduced by Abraham Maslow [27]. The hierarchy of needs are prioritize (goals), organize (successes), streamline (work/tasks), economize, and contribute (create a difference).

Project Management (PjM) is the science and art of organizing all the components of a project. It is the application of processes, methods, skills, knowledge and experience to achieve specific project objectives according to the project acceptance criteria within agreed parameters [28]. Resource management (RM) as part of project management is all about doing more with less. RM is centered on optimization and efficiency. *Risk Management (RsM)* is the process of identifying, monitoring, and managing potential risks, optimizing success by minimizing threats and maximizing opportunities and outcomes [29].

Motivation and Incentive (MotInc) Motivation is derived from the word 'motive' means needs, desires, or efforts. This is the method of inspiring people to achieve goals. The main tool of motivation for efficiency is the incentive. Incentive is an increase in performance and potential for greater action. It increases performance and brings new enthusiasms [30].

International Experiences

Currently, AI technologies play an influential role in the development of public services and support civil servants in public administration. *The United States* has embraced AI to automate various administrative tasks (automating government processes with AI), such as processing tax returns and issuing social security benefits. This automation has streamlined operations and reduced processing times. This

reduces processing times and improves accuracy [31]. *China’s* AI policies prioritize the speeding up of technology development, data collection and implementing pilots, risk management, data privacy, and accountability [32]. *Estonia*, a global leader in e-governance, has seamlessly integrated AI into its public services. The country's X-Road data exchange platform facilitates secure data sharing across government agencies, enabling AI-powered applications like chatbots, predictive analytics to enhance service delivery [33]. *In Korea*, government announced National Strategy for AI on December, 2019, which uses AI technologies across all spheres, starting with industry. Generally, 100 government action tasks in 9 strategies in 3 areas: AI ecosystem, AI utilization, and people-centered AI [34]. In 2020, the government adopted the Digital New Deal which envisions state-led industrial and educational efforts on the potential opportunities in AI. Government designated five universities as AI Engineering schools. The government supported the creation of an AI-oriented startup incubator to help develop emerging AI businesses. *The UAE* has launched AI-powered initiatives, including the Smart Dubai initiative and Abu Dhabi Artificial Intelligence Strategy. The initiatives are aimed at transforming the UAE into a global leader in AI using the following approaches: using AI to improve the efficiency of government services, such as issuing visas and passports, developing personalized education and training programs; improving urban planning and management; tracking traffic congestion and developing transportation solutions [35].

Discussions and Findings

The result supported our analysis in certain specific direction of AI-based technologies, and also previous initial research by Zeynep Engin et al., [36]. A review of the literatures covering articles available in research databases was completed using the PRISMA protocol for literature reviews, 60 articles within the scope of the study out of a total of 210 studies. In addition, results demonstrate a growing trend of interest in AI in government services, with Singapore, US, China, UK, India, Japan, Korea as the most active countries.

The conducted survey results showed that, totally 125 respondents responded following answers:

96.7% respondents answered to question “*Have you heard about AI?*” – *yes*

71.55% respondents answered to question “*AI as digital technology provides smart, secure, fast, efficient and convenient public services*” – *yes*.
31.7 % respondents answered as *maybe*.

82.1% respondents answered to question “AI-driven technologies effectively automate administrative tasks and services and help civil servants – yes

81.1% respondents answered to question “Do you think there is a need for clear legislation and strict regulation for the use of AI in public services? – yes

69.9% respondents answered to question “Use of AI increase efficiency through Algorithmic approach (Innovation & innovativeness and Administrative approach (Leadership and smart management – yes

89.3% respondents answered to question “For implementation of AI is important to learn international best practices, policy and strategies – yes

75.2% respondents answered to question “Do you think AI technologies can be an assistant or threat for people and government? – assistant for both side

“Do you think benefits of Implementation of AI in Public Administration? – Efficiency (84.4%), digitalization of Public administration (63,9%), productivity (58.2%), Trust (31.1) and others

Do you think disadvantages of Implementation of AI in Public Administration? – Top issues are Cyber threat (66.7%, Human replacement (58.5%, Expensive cost (46.3%), Ethics (43.9%) and so on.

Conclusions

Nowadays, AI is being used to design better policies, increase communication and engagement with citizens, improve the speed and quality of public services. Analyses show that, using of AI technologies in the public sector is still in its early stages, but it has the potential to reform the way that public services are delivered. The contributions show that AGA-AI approach has a positive effect as follows.

Inn=Inness+DIIn+AI+ML+DL+BiD+DSc+CyS+++Ldp=SmM+HCM+PM+S tM+TM+RsM+PjM+MotInc +++ Digi+Legis=DGov&Scy+StrL+AdvExpn = result> Smart, secure, fast, efficient and convenient state services to citizens

In addition, the contributions (Fig.1.) are: this is a new approach in modern public service development and management; Algorithmic pillars develops people’s mind, improve public services quality; Administrative pillars improves civil servants’ performance and achievements; Legislation part as a fundamental core supports AI ethics and regulations. Moreover, AI applications have key influential factors such as AI-based knowledge management software, AI process automation systems, virtual agents, predictive analytics, recommendation and autonomous systems, intelligent digital assistants, and cognitive security analytics, etc.

In addition, recommendations on adoption of AI technologies in government services: Automating public sectors one by one from a key service that will have significant outcomes; Explaining the pros and cons of AI by providing training improves the quality, and efficiency of public services; Preparing specialists for the future as data scientist, AI, ML experts, managers and software developers, cognitive scientists, data analysts, and digital marketers, cloud computing professionals.

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